
EGYPTIAN MEDIA LANDSCAPE: EXAMINING THE INTERACTION BETWEEN PRINT AND SOCIAL MEDIA

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Abstract

This study explores the relationship between Egyptian journalists and social media through a survey conducted in July and August 2018 on a sample of 120 journalists working in major national and private print and electronic newspapers and news sites. In-depth interviews were also conducted with editors and media professionals. Findings indicate a growing trend among journalists to use social media, particularly Facebook, primarily to promote newspapers and press content rather than as a source of information. Respondents emphasized the importance of credibility over speed to avoid publishing false news. While social media is being used as an information source, many journalists expressed concern that the future may favor social media over traditional media, highlighting the need for the industry to develop new strategies to adapt.

Keywords: *Social media, Social communication networks, New media, Traditional media*

1. INTRODUCTION

1.1. Emergence of Social Media

Web 2.0 technologies have enabled users to interact with each other, engage and collaborate in making media rather than just consuming it negatively. This has resulted in the emergence of social communication networks with a participatory media culture providing space for users to share content, links, and images beside news, information and commentary on the current reality (Hermida, 2012).

Wikipedia was one of the first to emerge in 2001 followed by Facebook in 2004 which is linking more than 1.4 billion users worldwide. Youtube was established in 2005 and is processing more than three billion search a month making it the second largest search engine after Google. Twitter has been launched in 2006 and allows users to exchange text, images and data.

Numerous studies have been conducted in different parts of the world that have proven that the use of social networks has become part of the daily routine of many journalists to get news and information or to reach the public who has begun to shift from traditional media to social networks.

Social networking has boosted the audience's value for traditional media for covering Breaking News and during the rapid developments of events such the China earthquake, the 2008 Mumbai terrorist attacks, and the 2010 Haiti earthquake, especially when telecommunications services collapsed or where they did not have Reporters.

In 2008, President Obama used Social Media in his campaign, demonstrating its importance in reaching the public at this early time (Kaplan A.M, 2015). The importance of social networking became apparent in June 2009 when the American State Department asked the administration of Twitter to postpone their periodic maintenance so that they can follow the Iranian protests. Also, the importance of social media became clearer when a Twitter user in Indonesia was the first to tweet about Bali (Indonesia) explosions in July 2009 before most of the main news organizations. The social networks have changed the news industry and the practice of journalism. Google, Facebook and Twitter competed for the audience with The New York Times, the Guardian, CNN, and the BBC which was previously described as the Fourth State. Now, researchers are calling social media "The Fifth State" (Alegandro, 2010).

By 2011, Twitter and Facebook were the most widely used networks in the newsroom. Many media organizations changed their editorial and organizational structures to adapt to social media (Hermida, 2010)..

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

A study by Villis concluded that the press should adapt itself to the requirements of the participatory environment on the Internet, and consider the users who share the content on the social media. Journalists should be given new knowledge and skills to meet the requirements of this participatory environment (Villis, 2017).

Mustafa Abdel Hay Hussein indicates that 96.7% of journalists working in 19 Egyptian newspapers use social media. Their main motive was to communicate with friends abroad and to obtain information. Facebook was ranked first followed by YouTube, Twitter, Google+, MySpace, and finally Instagram (Hussein, 2016).

Santa and Hopp found that journalists in all medium and large American newspapers are ranking Twitter higher than Facebook. Twitter's value is related to its use to inquire about followers, research and activities related to communicating with sources and using them as sources. The value of Facebook is tied to their use for asking about friends not as a source, and to carry out background research not to get ideas for the story. However, the rules of work and organizational constraints in the newsroom restrict journalists' use of social networks (Santa &Hopp 2016).

A study by Cision Company surveyed journalists in seven Western countries to discover how journalists use social networks. Most of them are in the category of promoters who use social networks to disseminate and promote content. They use it to interact with public, monitor media, follow current events, conversations or chats about their content, and reading posts of people whom they are following (Morrison, 2016).

Cokley's study about the employment of journalists in Australia found that job opportunities in the press increased in 2013, but there has been an increase in demand for media consumers. The results suggested that if journalists and publishers aim to enhance their readership levels, they should reduce their traditional focus on "information" and increase the ability of their readers to share their electronic content

and exchange it on social networks. It recommended entering "sharing studies" in the curricula of journalism (Cokley, Gilberth, Jovic, & Hanric, 2016).

A survey for 250 Egyptian journalists found that 53.6% of the respondents use social media in their work as an important source of information.

In Gaza governorates (Palestine), 98.7% of journalists use social media. Facebook came in the forefront of the most used networks by 87%. Respondents said that they prefer firstly to share political and secondly religious topics via Social Media (Safadi, 2015).

The journalists interviewed by Hermida recognized that they shared the media space with many outside the profession. They showed implicit understanding for the importance of deviation from the traditional role of gatekeeper. They also recognized that newsrooms have adapted to the new influences of participatory and social media. Public participation has been described as complementary, not as competent to the professionally produced content. (Hermida, 2015).

An analysis of seven American major media entities adopted Twitter as a new source of information during 2011 and 2012 demonstrated that journalists embraced Twitter as a new channel for information gathering. TV frequently cited Twitter as a sole or a primary source. However, despite active usage of Twitter overall, journalists in both TV and newspapers maintained conventional routines by relying primarily on Twitter accounts of official sources (Moon & Hadley, 2014).

A Content analysis of two Belgian newspapers published in the north of Belgium (De Standard and De Mogen) in 2013 showed that the number of topics that refer to social media as a source reaches five topics a day. It refers to Facebook, Twitter and / or YouTube, either as part of the topic or as a source, or both. Facebook and Twitter have popularity as sources in newspapers more than YouTube. The study concluded that social media has become part of the daily routine of journalists in news gathering (Paulseen & Harder, 2014).

A study about Indian media coverage of anti-corruption movement known as Anna explains how the use of mobile and social media platforms by its organizers influenced the traditional media coverage of the protests and made them jump into the vehicle of this movement (Rodrigues, 2014).

Twitter was found to be a convenient and cheap source for British and Dutch journalists who gather information from sites and insert them in their newspapers. Tweets have been heavily included, as quotations, in news coverage since Twitter began in 2007 until 2011. Twitter allowed journalists to stay connected to their sources, approaching important figures, follow specific users, and discuss topics. (Broesma & Graham, 2013).

The national survey of Irish journalists showed that social networks became part of the newsroom, and that about half of journalists use it several times a day. 99% of those polled said they use one or more of social networks professionally. Twitter was the most widely used. It was found that sports journalists are the most active on social networks platforms. Many journalists agreed that the use of social networks saves time, and make them more engaged with their audience and peers. (Heravi, Harrower, & Boran, 2014).

Thomas (2013) found that social networks made the press something different in terms of speed and accuracy. The study stressed that the press cannot live without social media, but social media can live without journalism. Journalists hoped to be trained on how to use social networks. (Thomas, 2013).

Currie surveyed 13 editors working in 16 news organizations. The study concluded that editors and the audience are challenging the traditional role of gatekeepers of news editors by representing the interests of the public in the newsroom. Editors often have a role to integrate social media into editorial practices, empowering news consumers as participants, and building online interaction by calling for comments (Currie, 2012).

In Egypt, Al Mawla found that although the relationship between new media and traditional media was competitive in the beginning, it is a complementary one. The traditional media tends to use new media tools to communicate with its audience, maintain its position and its presence on the media map, as well as the desire to add a new segment to its audience, and having ideas for articles. Besides, traditional media tries to renew itself by quoting some of the features of the new media, and to achieve harmony and coexistence with it. In addition, the new media represent a broad archive for journalists. In contrast, the new media uses the traditional media to support its published material (Al Mawla, 2012).

A survey for 135 journalists from around the world via Linked-in and about 20 press contacts through Facebook and e-mail found that journalists are starting to benefit from the social communication networks in getting on news and circulating it. Respondents' defined multimedia, editing video and digital stories are new required skills journalist should master. In addition, news room must change (Alegandro, 2010). The events in Iran in 2009 showed the importance of social networks for the traditional media, especially when the Iranian authorities restricted the movement of Western correspondents and intensified censorship of active blogs. The traditional media achieved three benefits of social networks: great possibilities to gather news and mainly photos, save time and a lot of confidence in some sites such as Twitter (Newman, 2009).

A survey of 100 media sites: 50 are Arabic and 50 are American found that Arab users' participation in providing information content was few. The Arabic sites did not care to explain to users how to communicate with them or how to upload their materials on their pages. In addition, they did not host their blogs or blogs of its media workers, and they missed many of the Interactive forms (Bakhit, 2009).

A survey of 130 Egyptian journalists using the Internet found that blogging as a communicative activity is widely accepted by journalists because it helps them to identify the issues and topics that are raised in debates. Blogs have gradually become a non-traditional source of journalism (Qodb, 2009).

Literature review showed that the interest in studying the relationship between social media and journalism began since 2009. These studies relied on the survey method for random samples of journalists. Some of these studies have mixed between social networks and online sites of traditional media, (Abdel Hay, 2016).

On the other hand, these studies have shown that Twitter is one of the most widely used networks by Western journalists, and that sports editors are the most active on social networking sites, while Facebook is more used by Egyptian journalists. Journalism in some countries, such as USA, imposes regulatory restrictions on the use of social media in the newsroom, which affects the degree of using these networks.

2.1. Research Problem

This study seeks to answer a key question: What is the nature of the relationship between the Egyptian journalism and the social media? Is it a competing or a complementary?

2.2. Research Objectives

The study aims to:

- Monitor the nature of the relationship between the traditional Egyptian press and the social media.
- Determine the extent to which journalists in the traditional and electronic media use social networks in their job.
- Explore how the traditional journalism benefits from social media techniques to maintain its existence.
- Find out whether electronic journalism use social media more widely than print journalism.

2.3. Research Questions

- Do Egyptian journalists use social networks in their work? How reliable are they?
- What are the press areas or fields in which journalists use social networks more than others?
- Are there differences between websites, Egyptian national and private newspapers in the use of social networks?
- How social media and the press benefit from each other?

3. METHODOLOGY

This research belongs to descriptive studies. It uses quantitative and qualitative techniques.

3.1. Tools

Survey, qualitative content analysis, and in-depth interview are used in this study.

3.2. Samples

A sample represents the big print and online newspapers and news sites were chosen. It included two national newspapers "Al Ahram" (The Pyramids) and "Al Akhbar"(The News), two private newspapers "AlMasry Al Youm"(The Egyptian Today) and "Al Youm Al Sabea" (The Seventh Day), ONA news agency and the news site "Masrawy" (the Egyptian). A qualitative content analysis was followed for some issues of these print and electronic above newspapers, besides in-depth interviews with 10 journalists: two editors-in-chief, one marketing manager, 5 social media officials, one video production official and one young journalist working in them.

A random sample of 120 Journalists working in the above newspapers and sites were chosen to answer the survey questions during July and early August 2018.

The study used Statistical analysis by computer on the statistical software packages SPSS win version 19 where simple repetitive tables and percentages, weighted averages, standard deviations, Chi square were used.

3.3. Egyptian Newspapers and Social Networks

The technological developments since the second half of the twentieth century have led to a decline in the circulation of newspapers in Egypt. Satellite channels attracted a large segment of the readers of newspapers. Then, websites and social networks came to attract the new generation of youth. Every issue of the two national newspapers "Al Ahram" and "Al Akhbar" distributed one million copies every day. Because of the dangerous competition of Satellite channels and the social media, all the Egyptian printed newspapers circulate 500 thousand copies a day (Hawari, 2018). This created a new reality for the Egyptian press that obliged it to reach the audience through establishing pages on those networks, and to establish specialized departments for Social Media.

Social networks specialists in Egyptian journalism agreed that the creation of social media sections in their newspapers started with the establishment of their websites.

About the importance of social networks for the press, editor-in-chief of the sports portal of Al Ahram (Al-Dardir, 2018) said: "The reader has become very lazy and does not even try to access the website of the newspaper. For that "Al Ahram" institution established a page on Facebook to promote all its publications and each publication established its own page. Now we have pages on Facebook, Twitter and Instagram, and more than this we share our news on those sites so we can reach the users. "

By following the two big national newspapers, Al Ahram and Al Akhbar, we find that they tried to keep up with the new trends but they reflect the impasse of national newspapers. Al-Ahram's portal publishes sections for young people such as "Videos", "Photo Albums" and "Varieties" which publishes soft news. "Al-Akhabar" portal published sections such as "Akhbar Al-Youm TV", "Videos", "Talk Show" and "Photo Albums" which publishes pictures, news and videos, but most of them relate to official personalities and official events. Al Akhbar also publishes a section entitled "Citizen Journalism". However, the numbers of those who follow "Al-Ahram portal" on Facebook are 322.933 followers, while the daily online site of "Al-Ahram" has about 3.4 million followers. Al Akhbar portal has 3.5 million followers.

As for the private newspapers, the number of its followers on social media exceeds the number of national newspapers. Mohamed El Hawary, head of television production unit and multimedia in AlMasry Al-Youm, said that their different publications have 40 million followers on the social media. The total number of Al Youm Al Sabea publications' followers is about 30 million (Hassan, 2017), "ONA" news has 719,829 followers; "Masrawy" news site has 6,837,259 followers on Facebook as well.

Since the promotion on social media is of a primary importance to private newspapers, the social media Section of Al Masry Al Youm follows the marketing department. Ayat Abdullah, marketing manager says that because the public does not enter directly on the newspaper's website, they started using social media in 2010 as a mean of communication between the public and the newspaper (Abdullah, 2017).

In response to the tendencies of social media audience, Al Masry Al Youm publishes on its website a section entitled "Al Masry Light", which publishes soft news including news of football players and stars, news of oddities and jokes. To attract readers to, Al Masry Al Youm publishes a permanent section for Public opinion's polls to discuss issues that interest people, as well as sections entitled "Videos", "Infographics", "Science and Technology", "Active", "Most Read", "Photo Albums" and "Matches".

"Al Youm Al Sabea"s site tends to be more serious than other newspapers, yet it tries to publish some light sections such as "Ein" (Eye) which is interested in stars' news, "Al Youm Al Sabea,s Albums", "Citizen Journalism" and the "Most read ".

Although the websites of the private newspapers have made an impact on the social networks, the paper editions have remained the same despite of the creation of some headlines such as "citizen journalism" in "Al-Masry Al-Youm", and on the electronic websites for Al Youm Al Sabeaand AlMasry Al-Youm". The "citizen Journalism" section in both newspapers looks like a "reader's mail". It publishes readers' problems, their suffering, and some of their creations. Social media editors in the two newspapers explained that citizens' messages are not published before ascertaining the validity of the allegations from responsible sources, and after re-drafting and editing.

4. RESULTS

4.1. First: Characteristics of the Study Sample

Two hundred copies of the survey were distributed, but the number of returned forms valid for analysis was 120 forms. The analysis showed demographic characteristics of the respondents as follows:

Table1. *Characteristics of the study sample*

Variables		Number	%	Total	%
Sex	Male	89	74.2	120	100%
	female	31	25.8		
Age	Less than 25 years	16	13.3	120	100%
	25- less than 30 years	33	27.5		
	30-less than 40 years	39	32.5		
	40-less than 50 years	17	24.2		
	50-60 years and above	12	10.0		
Did not mention age	3	205			
education	university	93	77.5	120	100%
	Post graduate	11	9.2		
	Didn't mention	16	13.3		
experience	Less than 5 years	30	25.0	120	100%
	5-10 years	35	29.2		
	More than 10 years	51	42.5		
	Didn't mention	4	3.3		

Job	Reporter, editor, designer,	106	88.4	120	100%
	Higher positions	14	11.6		
Institution	Al Ahram	19	10.8	120	100
	Al Akhbar	20	11.6		
	Al Masry Al Youm	18	15.0		
	Al Youm Al Sabea	17	14.2		
	Masrawy	11	9.1		
	ONA News Agency	9	7.5		
	other	6	5		

The table shows the following:

- The percentage of male journalists exceeded the percentage of females in the sample, 74.2% males and 25.8% females. This reflects the reality in the field of journalism where male journalists are more than females.
- The majority of respondents (88.4%) are young in the age category between 25 and less than 40 years old. Therefore, they are occupying posts of editor, interpreter or reporter. They represent the broad base of those who work in journalism. Higher levels (11.6%) are occupying posts of editor-in-chief, deputy Editor-in-chief, general manager of the editorial board, supervisor or responsible of a page. In terms of academic qualification, the majority (77.5%) has university education, and a small percentage (9.2%) has postgraduate degrees: master or PhD. In terms of academic specialization, 46.7% are graduates of colleges of mass communication and media departments, 5% are of other specialties, while 25.8% did not mention their specialty.

4.2. Uses of Egyptian Journalists for Social Networks

Respondents were asked whether they use social networks, their answers were as follows: Yes: 112 respondents (93.3%).

No: 8 respondents (6.7%).

4.3. Time Spent in Using Social Networks

Journalists were asked to define how much time they spend with social networks; the answers were as shown in the following table:

Table2. Time journalists spend to browse social networks

Time	Frequencies	%	Ranks
More than 4 hours daily	46	30.3	First
2h - less than 3 h daily	23	19.2	Second
One – less than 2h daily	17	14.2	Third
Less than one hour daily	14	11.7	Fourth
3h- less than 4h daily	13	10.8	Fifth

Other	7	5.8	sixth
Total	120	100	

The above table shows that about one-third of the sample is heavy users spending more than 4 hours a day browsing social networks. In the other category, one respondent in ONA added he uses it all the day while another says he uses it more than 10 hours per day. The rest of the journalists are of medium to high use.

4.4. The Most Widely Social Networks Used in the Egyptian Press

Survey asked respondents to identify the networks they use; the results were as shown in the following table:

Table3. *The most widely Social networks used Egyptian journalists*

Social Network	Mean	Standard Deviation	Order
Facebook	3.65	.96	First
YouTube	2.66	1.71	Second
Twitter	2.26	1.62	Third
Google+	2.23	1.89	Fourth
Instagram	1.65	1.74	Fifth
Wikis	1.14	1.56	Sixth
RSS	.75	1.56	Seventh
Blogs	.5	1.08	Eighth
Fliker	.31	.84	Tenth
Other:	.14	.93	Eleventh

As Facebook is the most popular among the Egyptian audience, the table shows that Facebook came in the first place. Egyptian journalists have to go to the Egyptian public wherever they are. For that, Egyptian journalists use Facebook to promote their newspapers and the content they publish. As a result all the Egyptian newspapers and news websites have pages on Facebook to reach the Egyptian public. This result correspond with the results of (Abdul Haye, 2016) while differ from the study of Santana and Hopp (2016), which reported that American journalists value Twitter more than Facebook, and with Graham (2013) that journalists in Britain and the Netherlands rely on Twitter in the first place, and use it as a source of information.

YouTube came in the second ranking, where journalists use it to download videos to attach it to their news or to upload theirs. Google+ occupied the fourth place because journalists rely on it to search for information, obtain photos and to verify the credibility of information and images sent by citizens.

As for the sites used by journalists more than once a day, 102 journalists (85%) reported Facebook several times a day. 64 journalists (53.3%) said they use YouTube more than once a day, while one of them defined 5 times a day. Followed by Google+, about 59 journalists (49.2%), Twitter 47 journalists (39.2%), Instagram 31 journalists (25.8%). The rest networks recorded low rates ranging between 5.8% and 3.3%.

Here the results of this study correspond with the results of (Abdul Haye, 2016) with respect to the rise of journalists' number who uses social networks in their job.

4.5. Reasons of Using Social Media in Journalism

Respondents were asked to mention their reasons among 20 reasons for using social networks. Their responses were as shown in the following table:

Table4. *Reasons of using social networks*

No.	Reasons	Freq.	%
1	To follow the developments of breaking news	77	72.2
2	To get on news and information	74	69.2
3	To know trending interest public opinion	60	56.2
4	To monitor public opinion's trends tendencies	59	55.1
5	To get on photos & videos	54	50.5
6	To promote and share their topics	52	48.6
7	To reach sources	49	45.8
8	To get on information about personalities	41	38.3
9	To get on information when coverage is restricted	38	35.5
10	To find ideas for my topics	37	34.6
11	To promote for my newspaper	29	27.1
12	To reply to my readers comments and chats	25	23.4
13	To express my opinion when it is not available	24	22.4

The above table shows that Egyptian journalists use social networks primarily to follow up the developments of events and secondly, to obtain information. To know the trending topics comes in the third place. To promote their content through sharing comes in the sixth ranking and to reach the sources. The results of this study differ from the results of Broesma & Graham (2013) which showed that journalists in the West use Twitter in writing leads of the news and the contents of the news itself.

Although the follow-up of developments of the events and access information sources came in the first and second order, the interviewed editors responsible for social media in the studied newspapers agreed that they do not rely on the social networks as a source of information because their priority is credibility, and the authenticity of the news, not to achieve beat. They are afraid lest they should be involved in publishing false news. They do not trust news published on social networks.

Abdullah, marketing director in "Al Masry Al Youm" explains the rules of publishing news from the social media: "we have a fact-finding platform based on whether we trust the person because he is credible, or because at least five people reported the same information, or we contact the sources to confirm the information".

Abou Al Hassan says that in Al Youm Al Sabea they do not use the social media as a source of information, but as a kind of alarm to pay attention to certain news. They fit with Santana's and Hopp's study (2016)

which found that American journalists stick to the US newsroom restrictions regarding publishing news from social media. It also matches with the study of Cision Company (2016) which found that most journalists in seven Western countries are in the promoters' category. Therefore, the press beat is ranked late. Egyptian journalists also are subject to newsroom restrictions which stipulate that news should not be published until its credibility has been verified by the relevant sources. They are satisfied of taking information from the official pages of government bodies, or the pages of football players and famous stars. They are interested in the trend stories on the social media, and ask journalists to follow and take care of them. This position of responsible social media in the Egyptian press matches with the results of Moon & Hadley (2014).

4.6. The Benefits of Social Media

The study sought to identify the extent to which the respondents benefit from the social networks. Their answers were as follows:

Table5. *The extent of benefits of journalists*

Extent of benefit	Frequencies	%
Too much benefit	67	55.8
Limited benefit	45	37.5
No benefit	8	6.7
Total	120	100

The table shows that slightly more than half of the sample has substantial benefits from social media, while about one-third of the sample has limited advantage compared to a small percentage that has no benefit. It was found a strong correlation between job and the degree of benefit. The Chi Square value is 47.76 and the degree of freedom is 18 at a significant level of .000. There was also a correlation between the extent of benefit and the section to which the journalist belongs, with a value of 48.66 and degree of freedom 30 at a significant level of 0.01.

4.7. Why Some Journalists do not Use Social Networks

The study sought to identify the reasons for the reluctance of some journalists to use the social networks. Surprisingly, some of journalists who use the social media and recognized its importance answered this question. Answers are shown in the following table:

The table shows that the journalists who use social media are more critical to it than those who are not using it. They have outperformed those who do not use them in the number of frequencies expressing their harm to the profession and journalism values.

The important reasons given by journalists for not using social Media are: they negatively affect the press in case of conveying its false news, their news lacks accuracy, and it is difficult to verify its credibility. Also it harms the journalist as it withdraws his role as a mediator between the public and the outside world. Besides, it is wasting journalist's time.

4.8. Creation of New Jobs Compatible with Social Network

Journalists were asked whether new jobs were created in their newspapers to keep up with the social media. 103 (85.8%) respondents answered affirmatively, while 17 (14.1% %) answered passively. About the jobs that were created, their answers were as shown in the following table:

Table7. *Jobs created in newspapers in response to technological development*

New jobs	Freq.	%
Social media editor	90	75.0
Video writer	75	62.5
Video editor	47	39.2
Infographic data specialist	42	35.0
A voice commentator	37	30.8
SEO specialist	32	26.7
Other	2	1.7

It is clear that a large percentage of journalists are aware of the existence of new jobs in their newspapers, notably a social media editor, a video editor, and a data journalist. The television production manager in Al Masry Al Youm said that new jobs have been created to cope with social networks. The most important of these are the Multi Media specialist, the television production manager, and the head of multimedia media and production unit. "Al Masry Al Youm" in August 2017 established a new sector called "Digital for the year 2020", whose mission will be to search how to benefit from social Media and Digital Media generally and financially.

4.9. The Relationship Between the Egyptian Press and Social Networks

The researcher borrowed the following expressions from foreign studies to identify the attitudes of Egyptian journalists towards the social networks. Their answers were as shown in the following table:

Table8. *Journalists' relationship with social networks*

Categories	Freq.	%	Rank
Accessing social media became a daily routine.	108	90	First
It is a mean to communicate with colleagues.	100	83.3	Second
It saves journalist time and effort.	77	64.2	Third
Encourages approaching unaccepted topics in my newspaper.	77	64.2	Third
Relationship between social media and traditional media is complementary not competing.	75	62.5	Fourth
Following social media increases & deepens culture.	73	60.8	Fifth
Social media helps improving journalistic production	71	59.2	Sixth
Social media makes press more transparent.	66	55.0	Seventh

Social media eroded censorship & gate keeping.	65	54.2	Eighth
Emergence of social media changed journalist's role.	63	52.5	Ninth
Social media helps journalism to keep its readers.	55	45.8	Tenth
Social media minded the gap between journalists and amateurs by allowing citizens to share their job.	55	45.8	Tenth
Social media can substitute traditional media.	43	35.8	Eleventh

The table shows that the attitudes of the respondents towards social networks are positive, and therefore it has become a part of the daily routine of about 90% of the respondents. From the point of view of some of them, social media saves the time and effort of the journalist, and allows them to break some taboos by allowing them and their newspapers to deal with issues and subjects, that were prohibited from publishing, after it was raised in social media. They see this leads to the erosion of censorship and the decline of the role of the gatekeeper, increases the margin of freedom of the press, helps to improve the productivity of journalists and increases their culture and deepens it (Fathy, 2018).

About 75 respondents (62.5%) of the sample believe that there is no conflict between journalism and social media. On the contrary, they believe it is a complementary relationship. The majority (64.2%) rejected the argument that social networks can become a substitute for traditional media. Meanwhile, Editor-in-chief of Al Ahram Sports Portal (Aldardir, 2018) described social media by saying "it is everything, it the most important thing at all and it is the future."

Al-Hawari said" after the media was the source of the social media, the verse has now turned upside down and the press has become interested in covering the popular stories published in the social media. In the beginning, the relationship was a competitive one. Journalism went out of the competition and the relationship diverted into dependency. The situation is not any more in the benefit of the print newspapers.

Al-Hawari suggested that newspapers should be integrated with each other to provide a new product for the segment that uses social media. The raised question now is: How do they can achieve integration and completion with Social Media?"(Al-Hawari, 2018).

Aboul Hassan added that the news reaches faster through the social media, so the exclusivity that was unique to some of the traditional media disappeared (Aboul Hassan, 2018).

Social media officials express their concern about the relationship with the social networks: Aboul Hassan says that the reader, who was basically linked to the newspaper, has become now linked through Facebook. As the public has become more linked to Facebook than newspapers sites, newspapers has to comply with the rules and the regulations imposed by Facebook. This represents a concern for the press because it turns it into a tributary of social media. If we cannot deal with social media rationally, it will turn into a ghoulish that swallows everything, and the press will become a follower (Abul hassan, 2018).

According to the editor-in-chief of Akhbar Al Youm Portal"social Media will pull the rug out from under the feet of the press". It has become the most important and fastest platform to take news from. Today, all

ministries, actors, stars and celebrities have social media pages, and after they resorted to the media to publish their news or to address their audience, they communicate directly with the public through the social media. Yet he sees that the relationship with the social Media is a complementary one.

He says that about 50-60% of Ahkbar Al Youm Portal visitors come to it through social media, and they can know people's tendencies through it. However, he sees the relationship between the press and social media is currently useful and can be described as a complementary, but in the future it could be otherwise (Galal, 2018).

However, we must not ignore social media. We have to deal with it. The social media allows ONA agency to interact with people. It does not threaten our existence because traditional media has credibility stems from a well-established tradition, concerned with ensuring the authenticity of the news and information before it is published, while social media can't do this (Sami, 2018).

4.10. Do Social Networks Benefit from the Press?

Respondents were asked about the benefits of social media from the press. They replied as follows:

Table9. *Areas of use of social media from the traditional press*

Benefits	Freq.	%
Social media uses press issues to support its materials.	78	65.0
Social media uses press to diversify its content.	46	38.3
Social media documents traditional journalism to acquire credibility	42	35.0
Social media profit from criticism & scandals published in newspapers	41	34.2

According to the respondents, social media benefits primarily from the traditional media's approach to issues and topics in support of its published material, in diversifying its content so that the reader is not bored and the scandals published in print media attract and entertain public.

5. CONCLUSION

The study aimed to explore the nature of the relationship between the Egyptian press and the social networks, whether it is a relationship of completion and integration, or a relationship of competition and conflict. It followed a quantitative and qualitative analysis. A survey of 120 journalists working in a sample of the major Egyptian national and private newspapers, and in-depth interviews with nine of the social media editors and online sites editors-in-chief and journalists.

The survey found that 93.3% of the sample uses social media, while only 6.7% said they do not need to use it, and 55.7% of the respondents said that they benefit from it but 37.7% said that their benefit is limited. This is due to the fact that journalists who work in print newspapers are less likely to use social media more than journalists who work in websites.

The study found that the first four networks used by Egyptian journalists are Facebook followed by YouTube, Twitter and Google Plus. Egyptian journalists differ from their colleagues in Western newspapers who use Twitter in the first place.

The Egyptian journalists use social networks to follow up events developments, get news and information, monitor public opinion, and obtain photos and videos. . Etc.

The interviewees confirmed that using social media became part of their daily routines that the role of the journalist changed with the appearance of social media. In addition to saving time and effort, it makes the press more transparent, led to the erosion of censorship.

Regarding the relationship between the social media and the press, the majority of journalists find it can be complementary, but social media specialists expressed their fears that it can swallow the press and become a substitute for traditional media.

The study opens new horizons for new studies on media education in the social media era: how curricula can be developed to prepare graduates able to work in a participatory environment, studying employment trends in traditional media, work standards and the future of traditional media in light of these technological developments.

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